

OVERVIEW AND DYNAMISM OF THE WORLDWIDE COMPOSITES MARKET

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Keywords: *Composites trends, technology development, innovation*

ABSTRACT

Overview and dynamism of the worldwide composites market.

Emerging opportunities from fast growing markets and dynamic regions will confirm the double-digit growth rate forecasted in the composites industry.

Yes, there is no doubt that composite materials are rapidly becoming a mainstream technology and materials of choice within many industries even though the general optimism in this worldwide industry is also facing challenges that are clearly identified.

The key drivers in the composite industry are ever challenging in terms of lightweight, reduction of raw materials and manufacturing costs, production with higher quality standards and sustainability in eco-friendly environment. To meet the expectations, several technological developments are focused on integrated design solutions, testing and analysis, life cycle assessment and composites process productivity to face a large scale production.

The main growth leverages will come from the:

- large consumption due to the increasing of human population and its needs with no limits,
- numerous innovations that feed the market and boost the use of composites instead of other traditional materials.
- technological transfers from the academic to the industrial world.

Key focus:

- Dynamics of different markets
- Trends and innovations
- Key applications sectors
- From academic research to industrialization